

Experimental Overview

BDT272 was tested for inhibition of hERG, hNav1.5 peak and late current, hCaV1.2, hKv4.3 (Ito current), Kir2.1 and hKvLQT1 (Iks current) using QPatch II automated patch-clamp. 6-Point concentration-response curves were generated using serial dilutions at concentrations up to 100 μ M.

Methods Summary

Compounds were solubilised to 33mM in DMSO before dilution in HBPS to 100 μ M. 6-Point concentration-response curves were generated using approximately 3-fold serial dilutions from the top test concentration.

Electrophysiological recordings were made from a Chinese Hamster Ovary or Human Embryonic Kidney cell lines stably expressing the full-length ion channel. Single cell ionic currents were measured in whole-cell configuration at room temperature (21-23 $^{\circ}$ C) using a QPatch II (Sophion Bioscience). The internal solution for all potassium channels contained (mM): 60 KF, 50 KCl, 10 EGTA, 10 HEPES and was buffered to pH 7.3. The internal solution for hNav1.5 and hCaV1.2 contained (mM): 140 CsF, 1 EGTA, 10 NaCl, 10 HEPES and was buffered to pH 7.3. The external solution (HEPES-buffered saline, HBPS) contained (mM): 138 NaCl, 4.5 KCl, 1.8 CaCl₂, 1.0 MgCl₂, 10 HEPES, 10 glucose, buffered to pH 7.4. Late sodium current was activated by application of 30nM ATX-II. Cells were clamped at a holding potential of -80mV before a depolarising step appropriate for each channel (see Table 1). Concentration-response curves were generated by cumulative addition of compound with concentrations low to high. Cells were repeatedly pulsed during this time at frequencies given in the table below. In all cases, steady-state inhibition was achieved before the next concentration of compound was added.

Table 1. Voltage protocols used

Protocol	Holding potential (mV)	Step (mV, msec)	Pulse interval (sec)	Comment
hERG	-80	+40, 2000/-40, 2000	10	hERG metric recorded at -40mV
hNav1.5 peak	-110	0, 10	10	
hNav1.5 late	-110	0, 20	10	Activated by 30nM ATX-II
hCaV1.2	-80	0, 50	15	
hKir2.1	-80	-140, 100	5	
hKvLQT1 (Iks)	-80	+40, 2000	20	
hKv4.3 (Ito)	-80	+40, 50	5	

Quality Control

The following QC conditions were applied:

(1) Individual cells with any of the following properties were excluded from subsequent analysis (1) seal resistances <500M Ω (2) ion channel currents <100pA (3) seal resistances that changed by >50% during the experiment

(2) Assay plates in which the IC₅₀ of the reference compound was outside of the expected range were failed.

Results Summary

IC₅₀ values were obtained from a 4-parameter logistic fit of the concentration-response data (Table 2, Fig. 1). Greater or less than values indicate where the potency estimates could not be fully resolved due to the concentration range tested. Compounds with activity less than 30% inhibition at the top test concentration were considered inactive.

Table 2. CiPA ion channel potency for each compound.

	IC ₅₀ μ M (% inhibition)	
	BDT-272	Reference
hERG	24.2	Quinidine (1.1)
hNaV1.5 peak	>100 (17)	Tetracaine (1.5)
hNaV1.5 late	>100 (6)	Ranolazine (27.0)
hCaV1.2	>100 (18)	Nifedipine (0.07)
hKvLQT1 (Iks)	>100 (42)	XE991 (1.3)
hKv4.3 (Ito)	>100 (31)	XE991 (7.9)
hKir2.1	>100 (21)	ML133 (14.0)

¹ Reference compound values were consistent with those presented in the literature (Elkins *et al.*, 2013 *J.Pharm.Tox.Meth.* **68**:11-122)

Figure 1. In each graph the log of molar concentration of test compound is plotted against the post-compound current, expressed as a percentage of the pre-compound signal. Data are normalised such that a value of 100% = no drug effect. Data from each cell are plotted, in each case N=3 or greater. The line of best fit is generated from the individual cell data points.